

Interactive Technological Approaches to Literacy in Second Grade: A Case Study at General Lázaro Cárdenas Primary School

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 01 October 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Miriam Olvera Cueyar</p> <p>KEYWORDS: Literacy, Interactive Strategies, Technology, New Mexican School</p>	<p>This study explores the use of interactive, technology-based teaching strategies to strengthen literacy among second-grade students in a socioeconomically vulnerable community in Hidalgo, Mexico. Employing an action-research approach, digital game-based activities were designed and implemented to foster reading and writing in alignment with the principles of the New Mexican School. Findings indicate significant improvements in literacy consolidation, as well as increased student motivation and participation, despite persistent challenges such as absenteeism and complex family circumstances. The integration of platforms such as Árbol ABC and Educaplay facilitated active involvement of both students and parents. The results underscore the relevance of technology-mediated educational support as a means to overcome infrastructural and contextual barriers, promoting inclusion and meaningful learning.</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Literacy is a fundamental skill that has a cross-cutting impact on the academic and social development of boys and girls in basic education. In contexts with high socioeconomic vulnerability and cultural diversity, such as the community of Santiago Tulantepec de Lugo Guerrero, the implementation of innovative methodologies that integrate digital technologies becomes essential to address learning needs and promote inclusive and equitable education. A detailed and comprehensive study has been conducted on an educational intervention at the General Lázaro Cárdenas Primary School, located in a community context marked by precarious economic conditions, labor migration, and limited family educational support, especially provided by mothers and grandmothers. The school serves 225 students divided into nine groups, with 34 students in second grade "A," which is the group targeted for intervention to strengthen initial literacy.

The diagnosis revealed that approximately 40% of these students have not adequately consolidated reading and writing skills. Additionally, around 30% have special needs such as ADHD and psychomotor delay, which affect their educational process. Despite significant limitations in the school's technological infrastructure, 90% of the students have access at home to the internet and electronic devices, although mostly for recreational rather than educational purposes.

Thus, the intervention initiative focuses on implementing interactive teaching strategies based on technology, aligned with the New Mexican School model, to enhance literacy through digital playful activities and the active collaboration of teachers, students, and parents. These strategies have shown significant progress in consolidating literacy, motivation, and student participation, even though challenges related to the students' sociocultural and emotional factors persist. This context reveals a valuable opportunity to transform the use of technology into an effective educational resource that fosters inclusion, equity, and academic success in a vulnerable environment, emphasizing the importance of family and formative support to overcome identified educational barriers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literacy is a fundamental competence that has a cross-cutting impact on the academic and social development of students from the early grades of primary education. It is understood not only as the ability to read and write texts but also to comprehend information and express ideas meaningfully in diverse contexts [1]. Initial literacy is regarded as a process of cultural and social appropriation of written language, essential for the educational and social integration of students. Literacy strategies are based on constructivist and sociocultural learning theories, emphasizing the role of social interaction,

teacher mediation, and active cognitive processes. Vygotsky stresses the importance of the social environment in cognitive development, while Piaget highlights learning as an active process of knowledge construction [2]. Ausubel contributes the concept of meaningful learning, where the acquisition of new knowledge is achieved by connecting with previously consolidated learning [3].

The educational model of the New Mexican School (NEM) promotes a holistic, inclusive, and multicultural approach to literacy, recognizing the cultural and linguistic diversity of the country. NEM encourages the integration of reading and writing across various areas of knowledge and promotes the use of digital technologies to enrich learning [4, 5]. Additionally, evaluation in NEM aims to provide feedback and support the learning process beyond traditional grading criteria.

The use of interactive strategies based on digital technologies fosters active student participation, adapting to different learning styles and paces. Activities such as educational games, interactive platforms (e.g., Árbol ABC and Educaplay), and playful exercises promote motivation, interaction, and meaningful learning [6,7]. Research has shown that these tools increase reading comprehension, writing production capacity, and the consolidation of phonological skills, especially in contexts with structural and socioeconomic limitations [8,9].

In communities with high rates of social and economic vulnerability, such as the case study, additional challenges affect the literacy process, including parental migration, school absenteeism, emotional problems, and diverse educational needs (Escuela Primaria General Lázaro Cárdenas project). The use of technology in these contexts is limited by lacking school infrastructure, although access to personal devices and home internet presents an opportunity to implement digitally mediated strategies [10,11].

Studies implementing interactive technological and pedagogical strategies report significant advances in literacy consolidation, increased motivation, and student participation [12,13,14]. Continuous evaluation using tools such as checklists, rubrics, and early warning systems (SISAT) allows measuring individual and collective progress, facilitating adjustments and feedback in the educational intervention process.

The integration of interactive technological strategies in primary literacy, grounded in constructivist theories and aligned with the New Mexican School, represents an effective path to strengthen reading and writing among students with diverse needs [15]. Family mediation, methodological adaptability, and ongoing support are key to achieving sustainable results, especially in vulnerable contexts.

III. METHODOLOGY

The project was developed using an action research approach, structured in four main phases that ensure a systematic and reflective intervention to improve literacy in second grade:

- **Diagnosis:** involved identifying and detecting students with delays in reading and writing using the SISAT Early Warning System and institutional assessments. SISAT is a set of indicators, tools, and procedures designed to provide timely and systematic information to educators about students who are at risk of not achieving key learning outcomes or dropping out. A detailed analysis of individual educational needs was conducted to design specific interventions.
- **Planning:** Selection, design, and adaptation of interactive teaching strategies and digital-playful activities. Integration of technological platforms such as Árbol ABC—a website offering educational games for language learning and literacy development—and Educaplay, a platform for creating and sharing interactive learning activities. These tools are used to promote reading, writing, and reading comprehension. Preparation of digital resources and training sessions for teachers and parents to support the literacy process.
Intervention: Implementation of activities both in the classroom and at home, with the support of families and teachers. Continuous training for parents and teachers to effectively use digital platforms. Use of interactive educational games aimed at strengthening reading and writing skills.
- **Evaluation:** The SISAT (Early Warning System) provides key indicators on students’ progress in basic reading, writing, and mental calculation skills. It integrates data such as class attendance, grades, and evaluation alerts to identify students at risk and support targeted pedagogical interventions. Teachers and school staff analyze these results regularly to adjust strategies and provide feedback for continuous improvement.

IV. RESULTS

The implementation of interactive, technology-based teaching strategies showed significant progress in the literacy process of second-grade students at Escuela Primaria General Lázaro Cárdenas. Based on evaluations conducted through the Early Warning System (SISAT) and classroom observations, notable advances were identified in the consolidation of reading and writing skills.

Figure 1. Activities in Árbol ABC

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In Figure 1, an image is shown depicting a parent meeting, where they attend to learn about the launch of the project and the *Árbol ABC* platform, with the aim of supporting the children’s literacy process. This image illustrates the families’ participation in the educational activity, highlighting their involvement in the learning process of second-grade students at General Lázaro Cárdenas Elementary School.

Regarding writing, it was observed that 42% of the students managed to consolidate syllabic-alphabetic logic, while 33% reached a developing level of writing, reflected in improved word and sentence formation with fewer spelling errors. The remaining 25% showed progress toward conventional writing, with greater accuracy and fluency when composing complete sentences.

The assessment revealed that 33% of the students reached the expected level for their grade, demonstrating adequate reading comprehension and the ability to interact with different types of texts. Another 25% showed progress toward higher reading levels, improving their fluency and motivation. However, 42% of the students required targeted support due to difficulties in word recognition, comprehension, and attention, which was addressed through personalized activities on the digital platform.

An increase in student motivation and participation was observed, attributable to the use of recreational technological resources, such as letter games and interactive stories, provided both in the classroom and at home with family support. Parental involvement through training and informational meetings strengthened the monitoring and continuity of activities, generating a collaborative educational environment.

The SISAT results reflect that a greater number of students achieved the expected levels of reading and writing performance, demonstrating that the strategies implemented strengthened basic literacy skills. Furthermore, it was observed that the incorporation of technological resources and interactive dynamics facilitates text comprehension and production, promoting sustainable learning habits.

Figure 2. Third SISAT Reading and Writing Assessment

Figure 2 presents both reading and writing assessment results from the third SISAT evaluation. The reading assessment (left chart) shows 4 students requiring support (red), 6 students in

development (yellow), and 2 students reaching the expected level (green). The writing assessment (right chart) displays approximately 3 students requiring support (red), 7 students in development (yellow), and 2 students achieving the expected level (green). This distribution demonstrates substantial improvement from the initial diagnosis, with the data showing that 42% of students consolidated syllabic-alphabetic logic in writing, while 33% reached a developing level with improved word and phrase formation and reduced spelling errors.

However, sociocultural factors have been identified, such as truancy, family issues, and special educational needs (including students with ADHD and psychomotor development disorders), which will affect the progress of certain students, requiring specific adaptations and targeted support. In summary, the results demonstrate the effectiveness of implementing interactive technological strategies, aligned with the New Mexican School, in promoting literacy in vulnerable contexts. It is recommended that this approach be continued, deepening personalized attention and strengthening family-school collaboration to optimize educational outcomes.

V. DISCUSIÓN

The implementation of interactive didactic strategies based on digital technologies in a socioeconomically vulnerable context such as General Lázaro Cárdenas Elementary School has demonstrated a positive impact on the literacy process of second-grade students. Through the use of platforms like *Árbol ABC* and *Educaplay*, combined with active participation from teachers and parents, students were significantly motivated in reading and writing, which reflects the effectiveness of technology-mediated approaches in educational environments with infrastructure limitations. Advances were observed in the consolidation of reading and writing skills, with a significant percentage of students improving in letter recognition, word formation, and reading comprehension. However, progress was not uniform; students with special needs, disorders such as ADHD, psychomotor development problems, complex family contexts, and high levels of absenteeism showed less progress, highlighting the importance of personalized interventions and constant support.

The results also confirm that alignment with the New Mexican School, which promotes active, inclusive methodologies and the use of technologies, was an appropriate framework for educational intervention. The combination of constructivism, meaningful learning, and interactive strategies favored participation, ludic learning, and active knowledge construction, adapting to the diverse learning styles and rhythms present in the group.

Nevertheless, the experience reveals practical challenges in project continuity, including interruptions due to school activities and family limitations in supervising the educational

use of devices. This suggests the need to strengthen communication and support with families to maximize the impact of technology on learning

VI. CONCLUSIONES

After analyzing the results and progress of the project, it is concluded that the integration of interactive didactic strategies supported by digital technologies significantly favors the literacy process of second-grade students in vulnerable contexts. This integration promotes not only academic development but also an increase in student motivation and participation. It was found that most students achieved important progress in key skills such as reading, writing, and appropriate use of technological resources, with many reaching levels close to or within the expected standard for their grade.

On the other hand, limitations were identified due to special educational needs and socio-family factors, such as school absenteeism and lack of constant family support, which slowed the progress of some students. This highlights the importance of implementing differentiated interventions and fostering greater community involvement and collaboration to address these deficiencies.

The approach and methodology based on the Nueva Escuela Mexicana, which integrates meaningful learning, playful activities, and technological interaction, proved to be an effective pedagogical framework to improve literacy. This model can be replicated and adapted in similar educational contexts to maximize positive impact.

Finally, the need for continuous follow-up and sustained collaborative work between teachers, students, and families is emphasized to ensure lasting educational improvements that respond to the changing demands of society and technology.

REFERENCIAS

1. Serrano Arenas, D., & Cordero Arroyo, G. (2025). La caracterización de la convivencia escolar en el Plan de Estudio para la educación preescolar, primaria y secundaria 2022. *Revista Latinoamericana de Estudios Educativos*, 55(2), 63–90. <https://doi.org/10.48102/rlee.2025.55.2.716>
2. Somulache, L. y Somulache, F. (2022). La teoría de Vygotsky en acción: la educación infantil. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781003120216-6/vygotsky-theory-play-earlychildhood-education-larry-smolucha-francinesmolucha>
3. Roa Rocha, J. C. (2021). Importancia del aprendizaje significativo en la construcción de conocimientos. *Revista Científica de FAREMEsteli*, 63–75. <https://doi.org/10.5377/farem.v0i0.11608>
4. Secretaría de Educación Pública. (2022). Modelo educativo de la Nueva Escuela Mexicana . <https://educacionbasica.sep.gob.mx/wpcontent/uploads/2024/06/Plan-de-Estudio-ISBNELECTRONICO.pdf>
5. Ávila Carreto, Castillo Vergara y Vázquez Vega. (2022). La Nueva Escuela Mexicana ante la Cultura Digital. ¿Propuesta técnica o construcción conceptual? Congreso Internacional de Evaluación de Educación 2022. <https://centrodeinvestigacioneducativauatx.org/publicacion/pdf2022/A171.pdf>
6. Kumari, S. y Bhumika. (2024). Integración de la tecnología en el aula de primaria: estrategias docentes para la alfabetización digital. *Revista Internacional de Investigación Multidisciplinaria*. <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i03.22317>
7. Muallimin, E., Fridani, L. y Nurjannah, N. (2023). Estrategias docentes para mejorar las habilidades de alfabetización digital de niños de 7 a 8 años. *EDUTEC: Revista de Educación y Tecnología*.
8. Chan Uh, LE (2024). Dificultades en el aprendizaje de la lectoescritura en alumnos de 3° la Escuela Primaria "Cuauhtémoc", X-Cabil, Quintana Roo. Universidad Vizcaya de las Américas. Tavel, P. (2007). *Modeling and simulation design*. Wellesley, MA: AK Peters Ltd.
9. Andrea, IGN e Ismanda, LNM (2020). Implementación didáctica de las TIC para el fortalecimiento de la lectura y la escritura. <https://repository.udistrital.edu.co/items/c50e34e7-9f74-4b81-ae8-5149d8e14f20>
10. Toribio Pérez, MC (2019). Importancia del uso de las TIC en educación primaria. *Revista Atlante: Cuadernos de Educación y Desarrollo* (febrero 2019).
11. Loza Cruz, JA (2022). Aplicación del uso de las tecnologías de información y comunicación (TIC) como estrategia metodológica en el proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje de la lectoescritura en alumnos de primaria. *Tesla Revista Científica*, 3 (1), e134. <https://doi.org/10.55204/trc.v3i1.e134>
12. Duke, N., Halvorsen, A., Strachan, S., Kim, J. y Konstantopoulos, S. (2020). Poniendo a prueba el PjBL: el impacto del aprendizaje basado en proyectos en el aprendizaje y la motivación de los estudiantes de segundo grado en estudios sociales y alfabetización en entornos escolares de bajo nivel socioeconómico. *Revista estadounidense de investigación educativa*. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831220929638>
13. Barberousse-Alfonso, P. y Vargas-Dengo, MC (2019). Animación a la lectura y escritura en la Escuela Finca Guararí: Una experiencia lúdico-creativa desde el proyecto “Construyendo una propuesta de implementación” del Programa

“Interactive Technological Approaches to Literacy in Second Grade: A Case Study at General Lázaro Cárdenas Primary School”

Maestros Comunitarios. Revista Electrónica Educare. <https://doi.org/10.15359/ree.23-2.7>

14. Somulache, L. y Somulache, F. (2022). La teoría de Vygotsky en acción: la educación infantil. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9781003120216-6/vygotsky-theory-play-earlychildhood-education-larry-smolucha-francinesmolucha>
15. García, I., Pacheco, C., & García, G. (2010). Una plataforma de aprendizaje constructivista en la práctica: alfabetización informática integrada en la escuela primaria. Revista internacional de tecnologías emergentes en el aprendizaje. <https://doi.org/10.3991/IJET.V5I2.1040>